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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND MARKETING SUCCESS OF OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN SOUTH SOUTH, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between corporate social responsibility and marketing success in the oil and gas industry in South, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. 301 copies of a questionnaire were distributed. The Multiple Regression Analysis Statistical tool was used with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23.0), discriminant validity (AVE), and Cronbach Alpha verified the internal consistency and validity status and the results were positive. The findings of the study showed that CSR is significantly related to marketing success in the oil and gas industry, thus enhancing profitability and market share. Based on the findings, the study, recommends that Oil and gas firms should continue to enlarge their capacity for interacting with stakeholders through interpersonal small groups and public communication strategies. The firms should strive hard to jettison divide-and-rule tactics, selective engagements, and fire brigade approach to community people and issues.

KEY WORDS:

Corporate Social Responsibility, Marketing Success, Oil and Gas Industry.

1.1 Introduction

South-South States by geo-political definition are states found in the Niger Delta region bordered by coastal waters of the Atlantic Ocean that are oil producing. Inclusive of these are Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Delta, Cross River, Edo and Rivers (Osunkun, 2000). This geo-political zone is Nigeria's largest oil producing zone, and one of the highly productive oil exporting zones in the World (UNDP, 1999). Environmental degradation in South-South States is traceable mostly to the operations of the international oil and gas companies in the region. These operations are related to petroleum resources exploitation to meet global energy needs that are leading to "a deep toxic stain" spreading through air (gas flaring causing black soot), water, and land on a universal scale. This has raised global consideration of how establishments in the oil producing areas to give back to the various publics and society of which they generate revenues from. Globally, oil and gas organizations are concerned with value re-investment to the society in appreciation of the contributions of the public to their growth, sustenance and survival.

Corporate social responsibility has gained an institutional status for regulators because of its linkage with compliance to law and ethical practices. It has acquired different meanings over time and combined some features or characteristics making it to represent set of obligations, responsibilities, stakeholder rights, and all forms of philanthropic activities from establishments (oil and gas firms inclusive) to the various publics (Moon, 2002). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) can be seen as a contribution to sustainable economic development while improving the quality of life of the people, workforce and its environment (Pranjali, 2011). CSR is used to establish good rapport with the public, protect eye striking profits, improve work life balance of employees, and prevent unforeseen risks, corporate scandals and possible environmental accidents. CSR is regarded as the organization's activity to make sustainable impact in society, and which in turn has the potential to create positive effect on the business organizations that engage in it. CSR is a business approach that views respect for ethics, people, communities and the environment, as an integral strategy that improves the competitive position of a firm (Obi, 2015). Over the past decade, a growing number of companies have recognized the business benefits of CSR policies and practices.

However, a number of studies have found a positive relationship between CSR activities and firm financial performance: Conesa et al. (2018) studied on corporate social responsibility and its effect on organizational innovation and firm performance: an empirical research in SMES and conceptualized CSR using ethical responsibility, legal responsibility, philanthropic responsibility and environmental responsibility; Vuta et al. (2019) focused on CSR and economic performance using environmental and social responsibility as dimensions; Rahizah et al. (2011) the importance of corporate social responsibility on consumer behaviour in Malaysia using economic responsibility, philanthropic responsibility, ethical responsibility and legal responsibility as dimensions; Feng et al. (2018) in their study on CSR used obligation to customer, community and employee as their working dimensions to operationalized CSR. In this study, we will embrace Economic responsibility and Legal responsibility as dimensions of CSR, considering its continuous validation by various scholars (Tsoutsoura, 2004; Ubrežiová, et al., 2015; Maignan, 2001; Jamali & Mirshak, 2007) and the peculiarities of oil and gas industry in Nigeria, with various players in and out of the country. It is on this backdrop that the current study wants to go into this study, to fill the knowledge gap that exists.

1.2 Research Problem

Over the years, managers of corporations have neglected the problems created by corporate firms to their varying stakeholders. These problems pose a lot of threat and often make life excruciating for the host community. An example of these problems is the persistent crises in the South-South States which led to destruction of lives and properties. The society claims that the social and environmental impact of corporations has affected them adversely and as a means of unleashing their vengeance they result in sabotaging and vandalizing of operating facilities, kidnapping of organizational members, some even go to the extent of suing the company for damages which in-turn affect the firm's profitability, market share and sales volume. Indeed some corporations are concerned about what they can take out of the society and de-emphasize the need to give back to the society.

The process of oil exploration, leading to gas flaring, oil spillage, crop and aquatic environment destruction as a result of careless abandon which the oil companies have adopted as a method, is the major cause of agitation by the host communities of oil companies. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the use of CSR has raised doubts as to the effect it has on financial sustainability or if companies are just diverting their time and resources to an unworthy task that would have no effect on its performance in the nearest future. Some missing gaps appear to exist in challenges of CSR dimensions, contextual factors and dimensions of the marketing success employed in the studies. Therefore, in order to evaluate the extent of impact of CSR of oil companies on community development in their host communities, this paper has raised. This approach makes the research work unique for better results and understanding of corporate social responsibility and marketing success, thus, seeks to clearly investigate corporate social responsibility influences with marketing success in the oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship that exist between corporate social responsibility and marketing success in oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria. In line with the above aim, this study has the following specific objectives to:

- i. Determine the relationship between economic responsibility and marketing success.
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between legal responsibility and marketing success.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Foundation: Stakeholder theory was fine-tuned and more systematic research on the different components that should be taken into proper thoughtfulness was added. According to Carroll and Buchholts (2003), the stakeholders can be sub-categorized into primary stakeholders (consisting of shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, business partners, host communities, future generations and the natural environment) and secondary stakeholders (made up of the local, state and federal government, regulatory bodies, civic institutions and groups, special interests groups, trade and industry groups, the media and competitors). However, the classification is quite capricious. Currently, Customers do not evaluate establishments based only on the features of their products and services, but also on what business activities they are engaged in, how their products are produced and the impact it has made on the society (Hartmann, 2002).

Stakeholder theory suggests that enterprises are motivated to widen their objectives to include other goals in addition to profit and wealth maximisation. Based on this theory, many establishments embrace a CSR program as a way to promote socially responsible actions and policies and to effectively respond to stakeholder demands (Maignan & Farrell, 2004). Motivation for satisfying stakeholder demands stems from the fact that addressing stakeholder needs can be correlated with a firm's survival, economic well-being, competitive advantages, and the development of trust and loyalty among its targeted customers (Mitchell et al., 1997).

2.2 Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Corporate Social Responsibility also called corporate citizenship, responsible business and corporate social opportunity is literally means a concept whereby establishments consider the welfare of the public where they deal business activities with by taking responsibility for the influence of their operations on customers, suppliers, employees, shareholders, communities and the stakeholders as well as the environment. There is a superfluity of definitions of CSR given by scholars and practitioners according to their business involvement and sectors. Some of the definitions include the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, which defines CSR as “the progressing obligation by an enterprise to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of work-life balance of the employees and their families as well as the local community and society at large” (Amao, 2014). CSR makes corporations responsive to the public other than just its shareholders. These public could include suppliers, customers, shareholders, and the environment, and host communities amongst others. Thus, the corporations are expected to take responsibility for their actions (if any) on the aforesaid various public. CSR treats problems relating to human rights violation, labour rights or standards, bribery, environmental degradation, green marketing orientation and corruption amongst others (Amao, 2008). In essence, CSR extends beyond the traditional and legal requests expected of establishments with regard to its impact on its various stakeholders.

Post et al., (1999 as cited in Motilewa & Worlu, 2015) define CSR as the meansthrough which a business establishment is held accountable for any of its activities that affect people, community andits environments.Crowther and Aras (2008) sketch out four differentdefinitions of CSR, firstly as the relationshipbetween global business establishments, governments ofcountries and individual citizens, secondly, as therelationship between a business establishment and thelocal society in which the enterprise operates,thirdly, as the relationship between the business establishment and its stakeholders and fourthly, a corporate' responsibility towards its future and that ofmembers of the society. Adeyanju (2002 as cited in Motilewa & Worlu, 2015) explainsthat CSR is concerned with treating the stakeholdersof a firm ethically or in a socially responsiblemanner.

2.2.1 Economic Responsibility (ECR)

In business institutions, economic responsibility is the basic unit in a business establishment (Carroll, 1979). To satisfy ECR towards society, enterprises should provide goods and services that society wants at reasonable prices. In addition, corporations have an ECR towards themselves, that is, making profits to be able to continue providing goods and services that the various publics needs and wants at reasonable and affordable prices. They also need to pay their workforce, increase shareholders' wealth, and take care of the interests of other firm's stakeholders (Carroll, 1979). Economic responsibility is seen as the basic commitment of business establishment to include oil and gas corporations. According to McAlister et al. (2003), the economy is influenced by the ways in which enterprise relates to its stakeholders, such as shareholders, employees, suppliers, product users, competitors, community, and even the natural environment. ECR lies in maximising not only shareholders' wealth but also other stakeholders' well-beings as well.

According to Maignan and Ferrell (2004), to be a socially responsible organisation when the economic achievements are not recognized first seem to be dangerous. Maignan and Ferrell (2004) highlighted for instance, the experience of the ice cream manufacturer Ben and Jerry's Inc., which has been repeatedly accused of neglecting economic performance because of its many philanthropic activities, the firm had set-backs and couldn't continue operation. Business enterprises have shareholders who demand a reasonable return on their investments; they have employees who want safe and fairly remunerations; they have customers who demand good quality products at a fair and affordable price.

2.2.2 Legal Responsibility (LR)

Corporate social responsibility is a subject that has links with many areas of law, including international law and European law, corporate law and corporate governance, tort law and contract law, procedural law, labour and environmental law, and criminal law. As business is an entity itself, it must also follow laws and rules. Every business establishment has a responsibility to operate within the ambit of the law set by the various commissions and agencies at every level of the government (Obi, 2015). All of these areas contribute importantly to the development of CSR, and ultimately to respond to the serious challenges that this world faces form manufacturing of products essential to mankind (Lambooy, 2014). According to him, legal responsibility (LR)relates to compliance with laws and regulations established by theauthorities, which set standards for responsible behavior – the codification of what society thinks isright or wrong. In carrying out their economic responsibility, enterprises are expected to work within the ambit of laws and regulations as a partial fulfilment of the "social contract" between establishments and society. Carroll (1991) stated that it is important for LR to be performed in a manner that is steady with the expectations of governments and laws complying with the various federal, state and local regulations. A successful business organization should be recognised as one that fulfils its legal obligations.

2.3 Marketing Success

Success can be defined as the achievement of an action within a definite given time. It can also mean completing an objective or reaching a goal. Marketing is a function and a set of processes that enables organizations to create, communicate, and deliver value to its customers (Hunt & Arnett, 2006). Marketing success occurs when a firm's competence in marketing constitutes a corporate resource (i.e., it contributes to enabling the organization to produce efficiently and/or effectively market offerings that have value for some

market segment(s) (Sternthal & Tybout, 2001). Corporations that develop a marketing competence are able to sustain the co-ordinated deployment of assets in a way that helps them achieve their goals (Sanchez et al., 1996). Marketing success is a fundamental performance dimension of the marketing organization which is generally considered among the most important priorities of each company. Marketing success has attracted a great deal of attention in academic and managerial circles (Nwokah & Ahiauzu, 2008; Nwokah & Ahiauzu, 2009; Gao, 2010; Halim, 2010). Considering success as a concept of return on marketing and cost (Muchiri & Pintelon, 2006; Navickas & Sujeta, 2006), marketing success should be defined as a ratio of return on marketing and marketing cost.

Marketing success is optimization of both short and long term organizational goals bearing in mind other factors. It is an organized process and procedure of achieving desired goal in a very competitive market. The topic of marketing success is considered to be a very up-to-date subject in the highly competitive environment.

2.3.1 Profitability

The word profitability is used to denote the amount of revenue a firm acquires. Profitability is used to measure firm's efficiency and marketing performance; it is a technique that can be applied in running a financial analysis of a firm (Alloy & Velnampy, 2014). Profitability can be described as the financial strength of a firm in a given industry within a specific time period (Kollmann, 2000). It is the degree of cost reduction and value maximization of a firm after a period of investment. Market share is the proportion of the total available market or market segment that is being serviced by a company (Mittal, & Michael, 2007). It can be expressed as a company's sales revenue divided by the total sales revenue available in that market. Despite its popularity as a dependable variable to measure business success, only few literatures can be traceable to it.

2.3.2 Market Share

Market share is the number of sales accruable to a particular enterprise within the total corporation sales usually measured in percentage; it is the delight of every business establishment to increase its market share as this indicates the higher inflow of revenue from customers' patronages. In a more explicit way, the Economic Times report (2015) defined market share as the percentage that goes to a business establishment out of the total purchases of the customers of a product. Following the definition, a typical example is where there are 1000 numbers of customers who buy oil and gas and 600 consumers buy from Total Plc, it indicates that Total Plc has 60% of the market share. In concurrence to this view, Dayan et al. (2010) stated that the success of any business establishment is generally related to attaining a greater height in its business goals such as return on investment and the maximization of shareholders wealth as well as increasing its market share.

2.4 Corporate Social Responsibility and Marketing Success

According to Rhou and Singal (2020) review of more than 170 articles on the relationship between CSR and marketing success, the impact of CSR activities on the stock market performance of oil and gas firms remains inconclusive. For example, Kang et al. (2010) investigation of the effect of CSR on the price-earnings ratio and Tobin's Q of oil and gas, airline, hotel, casino, and restaurant industries arrived at mixed findings. Based on the review by Rhou and Singal (2020), stakeholders of CSR activities that have been mostly investigated are environment, customers, employees, and communities. Although the effect of pandemic-related CSR on the stock prices of oil and gas firms is not fully understood, previous studies of CSR toward customers, employees, and communities (i.e., stakeholders vulnerable to pandemics) provide a theoretical basis to this inquiry. The study carried out by Herremans et al. (1993) shows that large U.S. manufacturing companies with better reputations for social responsibility outperformed companies with poorer reputations in the period 1982-1987, and provided investors better stock market returns at a lower risk. According to tens of American, European and Japanese business managers, the future belongs to those who create a dynamic and integrated organization that is capable of achieving specific effects and capable of being socially responsible (Mizera, 2008). Dhaliwal et al. (2014) discovered that a negative association exists between CSR disclosure and the cost of equity capital. This relationship is more pronounced in stakeholder oriented countries.

2.4.1 Economic Responsibility and Marketing Success

Economic responsibilities relate more to production of goods and services needed for exchange and transaction purposes at fair prices for the satisfaction of enterprise profit objectives as commitment to investors, through the satisfaction of identified target market; legal responsibilities impose obligations to respect statutes and regulations of governments, the ethical responsibilities expect businesses to acknowledge and observe to meet other societal expectations that are not expressly stated as part of documented law while the voluntary responsibilities are additional behaviours and activities that society finds desirable and that the value of the business dictate (Bateman & Snell, 1999). The economic face of good CSR means establishments are profitable, carry their own weight, and fulfil their ECR. Often times increasing profits is not discussed in terms of CSR. Carroll (2006) argues it is a necessary concept.

Ho₁: Economic responsibility has no significant relationship with profitability in oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria.

Ho₂: Economic responsibility has no significant relationship with market share in oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria.

2.4.2 Legal Responsibility and Marketing Success

Legal responsibility involves discharging commitments that are primary functions of a role and moral responsibility involves discharging obligations that are associated functions of the role. Secondly, For instance, failure in a food safety operation is usually followed by lawsuits and unflattering publicity which results in a significant decrease in sales and loss of market confidence (Swanger & Rutherford, 2004). In contrast, CSR activities, such as disclosure of nutritional and ingredient information (Fakih et al., 2016), use of non-genetically modified food (Lu & Gursoy, 2017), and suggestion of healthy alternatives (Lee et al., 2014), that show oil and gas firm's concern for societal well-being may bring extra benefit by increasing marketing success. In the era of COVID-19, customer safety and well-being are particularly salient components of CSR given the changes in people's daily routines (Wen et al., 2020). Oil and gas firms' ability to look after customers from infection is critical for rebuilding market confidence to survive the crisis (Hao et al., 2020). Consequently, the following hypotheses were formulated:

Ho₃: Legal responsibility has no significant relationship with profitability in oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria.

Ho₄: Legal responsibility has no significant relationship with market share in oil and gas industry in South South, Nigeria.

2.5 Empirical Review

Conesa et al. (2018) studied on corporate social responsibility and its effect on organizational innovation and firm performance: an empirical research in SMES. Population of 552 Spanish firms. Results show that CSR is positively associated with organizational innovation and firm performance and that organizational innovation mediates the relationship between CSR on firm performance. These findings indicate that CSR is an important driver for firm performance mainly by enhancing organizational innovation. Vuta et al. (2019) focused on corporate social responsibility (CSR) becomes central all over the world, being influenced by various factors, such as economic and employment crisis, fiscal issues, increasing competition, but also the interaction of environmental and social components with the economic performance. The analysis used data for 61 companies listed on Bucharest Stock Exchange for 2015-2017 timeframe, and the analysis was conducted using panel data regressions. They believe that the obtained results are explained by the companies' focus, especially the ones with solid financial status, on the implementation of measures that are associated with bio-economy, targeting a reduced environmental impact, and with social programs and activities. Rahizah et al. (2011) studied on the importance of corporate social responsibility on consumer behaviour in Malaysia. The definition of CSR was adopted from Carroll's questions were distributed, with 193 returned for analysis. The results showed significant positive relationships between all of the variables used in measuring CSR and consumers' buying behaviour.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section of the study presents a detailed explanation of the procedures, methods and techniques used. Also, it entails the overall research plans and designs that guided the progression of data collection and the choice of approaches used in research to collate data. However, this study will be concerned with quasi-experimental research. This paper is a quasi-experimental study, and we will adopt the cross-sectional survey research design. The total population in this paper is oil and gas firms in South-South, Nigeria. The population cuts across Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross Rivers, Edo, Delta and Rivers States. For precision and availability of required data, the study will consider only major oil and gas downstream firms that have their operational bases in South-South States of Nigeria. According to ministry of petroleum and Natural Resources, there are ten (10) major oil and gas downstream firms in South-South States of Nigeria. They include; Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited (MOPNU), Total Petroleum Nigeria Limited (TPNL), Texaco Overseas Petroleum Company of Nigeria Limited (TOPCN), Eroton Ltd (EL), Conoil Nig Plc, Forte Oil Plc, MRS Nig Plc., Oando Plc. Rainoil and NNPC (mega) stations of the six south-south states of Nigeria. This is premised on information obtained from the ministry of petroleum and Natural Resources in Nigeria. Information gathered from the human resources departments of each of the firms revealed that there are one thousand two hundred and twenty-three (1223) top level managers which are referred to as accessible population of the firms. Summary of the accessible population is represented below:

Table 3.1: Number of Accessible Population

S/N	Name of firms	RS	BS	CRS	AIS	DS	ES	Total	Sample Size
1	Conoil	29	28	26	24	20	26	153	38
2	Eroton	18	11	12	14	9	13	77	19
3	Forte	28	21	19	32	26	28	154	38
4	Mobil	32	24	27	25	28	19	155	38
5	MRS	32	21	19	30	28	24	154	38
6	NNPC Mega	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
7	Oando	31	22	20	29	25	26	153	38
8	Rainoil	27	7	16	19	15	12	96	24
9	Texaco	28	15	18	22	15	22	120	29
10	Total	32	26	24	26	27	20	155	38
	TOTAL							1223	301

The researcher employed Taro Yamen Formula to get 301 as sample size which were allocated to the various firms selected.

The questionnaire was subjected to a validity and reliability analysis. For the validity tests, the statement items were tested for discriminant validity (average variance extracted: AVE) based on 0.50 threshold. On the other hand, Reliability measures consistency and stability of instrument over time. In order to determine the consistency and stability of instrument, this study ensured a test-retest technique was implemented using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability co-efficient.

Table 1 Properties of the CSR and marketing success Instruments.

Constructs/indicators	Standardized loading(λ)	λ^2	AVE	CR	Cronbach Alpha
Economic Responsibility			0.64	0.89	0.802
ER1	0.895	0.801			
ER2	0.775	0.601			
ER3	0.717	0.514			
ER4	0.801	0.642			

Legal Responsibility			0.63	0.87	0.889
LR1	0.912	0.832			
LR2	0.813	0.661			
LR3	0.727	0.529			
LR4	0.719	0.517			
Profitability			0.74	0.92	0.811
P1					
P2	0.878	0.771			
P3	0.797	0.635			
P4	0.897	0.805			
	0.867	0.752			
Market Share			0.78	0.94	0.799
MS1	0.887	0.787			
MS2	0.883	0.780			
MS3	0.858	0.736			
MS4	0.910	0.828			

Evidence on the outputs from the factor analysis as shown in Table 2 present the standardized factor loading values of all items were above the value of 0.50. Additionally, composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) were computed using the standardized factor loadings. All these values were above the threshold value of 0.70. Moreover, the AVE value was calculated for each variable. The AVE values were above 0.50, which was acceptable. It is also expected that CR is higher than AVE outputs. Also the calculated AVE and composite reliability as well as SPSS output of Cronbach’s Alphas for the sixteen (16) statement items demonstrated a high level of reliability on the constructs of corporate social responsibility and market success. All items loadings were above 0.70.

The data analyses was done using Multiple Regression for testing the hypotheses

4.0 Data Analyses and Presentation

Table 3 showing the relationship between corporate social responsibility and market success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria.

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted (R ²)	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
1	.849	.721	.696	12.86962	26.451	.000**
2	.852	.726	.699	13.46616	27.592	.000**

Regression Model 1: $P = [(0.362ER) + (0.389LR)] - 5.125$

The model 1 revealed the linear relationship between economic responsibility (ER), legal responsibility (LR) and profitability (P). The result indicated a regression relationship (R) = 0.849 as well as coefficient of determination (R²) = 0.721 which was equivalent to 72.1%. This showed that a positive and strong relationship exist between the variables as indicated in the decision rule. This further entails that 72.1% variation can be explicated by factors within the model used for the study while the remaining 27.9% can only be expounded by other factors of the model used for the study. The f-ratio (F1, 301=26.451) showed significant effects in

existence and this revealed the strength of the model used for the study. The t-ratio showed significant of ER and LR to the present status of profitability. This result revealed that CSR made significant contribution to profitability. Furthermore, the probability value (p-value) is less than ($<$) 0.05, we therefore reject the established null hypotheses one and three that no significant influence of ER and LR on profitability of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria.

Regression Model2: $MS = 4.755 + [(0.439ER) + (0.567LR)]$

Model 2 showed the significant relationship between ER, LR and Market Share (MS). The results revealed a linear regression relationship ($R = 0.852$ and $R^2 = 0.726$ which was equivalent to 72.6% and it stands as the explanatory power of the model used for the study. The findings revealed a positive and strong relationship exist between the variables. It means that 72.6% variation can be explained by factors within the model used for the study while 27.4% can only be explained by other external factors. The f-ratio ($F_{1, 301} = 27.592$) showed significant influence in existence and it explained the strength of the model. The t-ratio showed significant of ER and LR to the present position of MS. This result revealed that CSR made significant contribution to MS. Also, the probability value (p-value) is less than ($<$) 0.05, we therefore reject the established null hypotheses that no significant influence of ER and LR on MS of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria.

4.1 Discussion of Findings

Positive relationship between Economic Responsibility and Marketing Success

Hypotheses one and two was designed to examine the significant influence of economic responsibility on marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria. Economic responsibility was hypothetically tested against profitability and market share and the results revealed that economic responsibility had a positive influence on marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria. There are several possible explanations for this result. For example, Vuta et al. (2019) asserted that economic and employment crisis, fiscal issues, increasing competition contribute immensely with economic performance. Rahizah et al. (2011) studies revealed a positive influence of ER on marketing performance and this shows how consistency the findings are. This consistency may be due to the fact that some oil and gas firms have gotten the climax of the organizational position where ER do not motivate again.

Positive relationship between Legal Responsibility and Marketing Success

Legal responsibility was statistically tested against the measures of marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria. Earlier, we hypothesized of the existence of no relationship between legal responsibility marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria. However, the present findings indicate the tendency of LR to positively influence marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria in terms of profitability and market share. The role of effective LR has overtime, been recognized by several authors as a strategic tool that enhances profitability and market share. The finding of this study is in accordance with the position of Baba and Onuoha (2018) that there is a significant link between organisational sustainability and the manifestations of corporate social responsibility. Babalola, (2012) that laws and regulations obligate firms to be recognized, adequate attention should be given to social accounting in terms of social costs and to comply with social responsibility should be enacted.

5.0 Conclusions

The result of the findings on the dimensions of CRS, namely ER and LR all contribute significantly towards achieving marketing success of oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria. In light of this, the study therefore concludes that:

- ii) The CSR initiated by oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria affect marketing success.
- iii) Economic responsibility significantly influence market share and profitability positively.
- iv) Legal responsibility positively correlate with market share and profitability oil and gas industry in South-South, Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, we put forward the following recommendations:

1. Oil and gas firms should continue to enlarge their capacity for interacting with stakeholders through inter-personal small groups and public communication strategies.
2. The firms should strive hard to jettison divide and rule tactics, selective engagements and fire brigade approach to community people and issues.
3. The firms should give attention to segments of the communities according to their strength, numbers and importance to firm's operations.
4. Oil and gas firms should integrate the various segments of the stakeholders into their information and communication apparatuses so that they can easily and readily become aware and knowledgeable about the firms community related activities. This will improve the perception of the people or communities or other stakeholders on their activities.
5. It further recommends that laws and regulations to obligate firms to be recognized,adequate attention should be given to social accounting in terms of social costs and to comply with social responsibility should be enacted.
6. Policy framework should be design for corporate social responsibilities in Nigeria by the government and ensure compliance by setting mechanisms and institutions for the implementation of CSR.
7. Companies in Nigeria particularly the profitable one should give greater priority to CSR. This has the tendency to assist them to survive and maintain their profitability.

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